

CFP Euralex “Queer(ing) Lexicography: towards truly inclusive dictionary-making?”

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We invite abstract submissions for papers on the topic of “Queer(ing) Lexicography” for the Euralex 2018 conference in Ljubljana, 17-21 July 2018

The role of dictionaries in society at large has been theorized and critiqued also with respect to hidden ideologies (e.g. Kachru & Kahane, 1995). Due to the fact that Unidentified Authorising Dictionaries (Moon, 1989) are often drawn on to legitimize and naturalize discriminatory discourses, they have been subjected to critical linguistic scrutiny. While feminist critique has yielded somewhat satisfactory results (Hoem Iversen, 2005), insights into constructions of sexuality are scarce (Pakuła, 2018). The few studies exploring non-heterosexual aspects of macro- and megastructures point to the inherent positioning of heterosexuality as an unquestioned norm and thus – in the educational context – might inhibit language learning, as is the case with textbooks and in-class interactions (see Pavlenko, 2004; Nelson, 2009). Somewhat disappointingly, there seems to be little resonance between what is done in the field of critical applied linguistics and metalexigraphy, as each camp preaches to the already converted (cf. Russell, 2012). This panel sets out to bridge these two (seemingly distant) worlds.

“‘Queer’ is one of a handful of terms in English that establish references by opposition and exclusion, not just by simple description. That is, instead of identifying properties that the object under discussion contains, calling something ‘queer’ suggests that it is out of place in some sense, that is excessive and overextended, that it disrupts and subverts an otherwise tranquil domain.” (Leap 1996: 101). The tranquil domain queer aims at disrupting and subverting in this panel is lexicography and the related disciplines involved in the mono- and interlingual dictionary-making. This panel on “Queer(ing) Lexicography” (Nossem 2018) aims at showcasing possibilities to overcome the apparent opposition between the anti-normative ‘queer’ that resists definition and can be seen as a “linguistic experiment, namely as a signifier without a stable signified” (Barrett 2002: 27), and the theory and practice of lexicography, with its focus on definitions and classifications (Nossem 2018).

In accordance with Motschenbacher, who explains that “Queer Linguistics transfers ideas from Queer Theory to linguistics” (2011: 6), we aim at further developing the field of Queer Lexicography by uniting ideas and concepts from Queer Theory and Queer Studies, and lexicography, i.e. by integrating an interdisciplinary heteronormativity research in the field of lexicography. By introducing queer approaches, and in the spirit of action research (Burr, 1995) we want to question normalized practices in lexicography, metalexigraphy, lexicology, semantics, corpus linguistics, and other linguistic fields, especially in their relation to dictionary-making. We propose to examine the linguistic manifestation of heteronormativity and, connected with it, binary gender and sexual identity discourses (Bing & Bergvall 1996 in Motschenbacher 2011: 21) as well as the instrumental use of dictionaries in public and media discourses with view of appreciating the multitude of sexual and gender identities of dictionary users (and compilers).

Papers which address the following topics are most welcome:

- Queer Studies and lexicography
- Gender Studies and lexicography
- Sexuality Studies and lexicography
- Critical heteronormativity research in lexicography
- (Anti-)normative approaches in lexicography
- Manifestation of dominant and minority discourses in dictionaries
- Dictionaries as authoritative tools
- Power and ideology in dictionaries
- Critical analysis of normative meaning definitions in mono- and interlingual dictionaries
- Queer approaches to semantics in relation to dictionary making
- Queer approaches to corpus linguistics in relation to dictionary making
- Dictionaries in public and media discourses of non-normativities

Please send abstracts no longer than 300 words (excluding references) to Eva Nossem (e.nossem@mx.uni-saarland.de) and Łukasz Pakuła (l.pakuła@gmail.com) by **26 November 2017**.

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